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**NOT ALL (LANGUAGE) NATIONALISMS
ARE BUILT THE SAME: THE CASE
OF FORMER YUGOSLAVIA**

The article discusses the language complex of Bosnian, Montenegrin, Croatian and Serbian standards (BCMS). The paper opens with the linguistic situation concerning the breakup of Yugoslavia, explaining that both the concepts of separate standard varieties and the concept of a unified “Serbo-Croatian” are equally nationalist projects. The relationship between these varieties is compared to some other language situations in the world (with Slavic languages in general, with Arabic languages, etc.). It then addresses different types of nationalism in the former Yugoslavia (primarily separatist and expansionist nationalisms) and criticizes liberal anti-nationalism, which in some instances functions as a cover for language nationalism (using Montenegrin as an example). A critique of some typical Western narratives on post-Yugoslav language issues is also given. The article concludes with a review of the very peculiar and interesting case of the so-called “Neo-Montenegrin” standardization.

Keywords: *standard, nationalism, ideology, Yugoslavia, BCMS, Croatian, Serbian, Montenegrin, Bosnian*

Introduction¹

In the most general sense, nationalism can be defined as an ideology that promotes (perceived or real) interests of specific nations, which are a special kind of modern “imagined communities” (Anderson, 2006). While nationalism is often criticized, especially from the more progressive political point of view, and even the very words *nationalism* and *nationalist* tend to have a somewhat negative connotation (which is not undeserved, to be clear), it also unmistakably encompasses a wide array of (sub)ideologies and policies and not all aspects of nationalist politics can be judged in the same way. For instance, the French (language) nationalism which promotes the exclusive use of standard French in France and the suppression of minority and regional languages is clearly not the same as Breton or Basque (language) nationalism in France, which stands up for the use of these languages. In one case, nationalism is espoused as an oppressive force, which seeks to minimize the use of other languages and the right of their speakers to speak their language, and in the other as an ideology fighting for a basic human right – a right to speak one own’s language (cf. Kapović, 2016: 25–26). It is the same when it comes to politics in general – national liberation struggles (e.g. against colonizers) and nationalist aggression on other countries are not the same and should not be treated in the same manner. One can hardly equate the nationalism of the oppressor and the nationalism of the oppressed. It is interesting to note that language very often plays a very important role in nationalism and thus it is very frequently featured even in non-linguistic treaties of nationalism (e.g. Anderson, 2006: 67–82).

Both political and language nationalisms in former Yugoslavia are quite notorious and have attracted a lot of international attention. Thus, for instance, the language situation in former Yugoslavia is discussed in introductions to sociolinguistics (e.g. Trudgill, 2000: 46–48) and is entitled monographs by scholars not from the area (e.g. Greenberg, 2004). In linguistics, a lot of works have been dedicated to politics and naming of what used to be called, and is still called that by some outside of former Yugoslavia, Serbo-Croatian (nowadays often

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BCMS: Bosnian/Croatian/Montenegrin/Serbian), while the topic is still quite controversial and explosive in the region (cf. e.g. Kapović, 2011b: 53–55; Kapović, 2020). In this paper, we shall try to present the different nature of (language) nationalisms, predominantly their modern versions, in all four central (Štokavian – in linguistic²/standardological³

² All four central ex-Yugoslav republics have the standard based on the Štokavian dialect, though non-Štokavian dialects are spoken in some of them (Čakavian and Kajkavian in Croatia and Torlak in Serbia). However, one should be aware that terms like Štokavian, Čakavian and Kajkavian should also be taken as provisory – (cf. e.g. Vermeer, 1982: 280–289; Kapović, 2015: 63–66 and Kapović, 2011a: 149–152).

³ The normative unity in the central states of former Yugoslavia has a complex origin that has to do with various political, dialectological and standardological reasons. First of all, in the 19th century, when the standard variety was decided upon, the name of the game was largely unity (even of all South Slavs), not divergence as it is dominantly today. Thus, Neo-Štokavian dialects were taken as the basis of the standard (see below for the term *Neo-Štokavian*), which are spoken in all four modern countries. This Neo-Štokavian was (i)jekavian (e.g. *lijepo bijelo mlijeko* ‘beautiful white milk’) in Bosnia and Herzegovina, Montenegro, and Croatia, while in Serbia (i)jekavian, despite attempts, could not take hold due to ekavian (e.g. *lepo belo mleko*), spoken in Belgrade and Novi Sad. A large part of Bosnia and Herzegovina is (i)jekavian, as well as practically all of Montenegro, so such a choice made sense there. In continental Croatia, the migrational Neo-Štokavian (i)jekavian dialect (often referred to as the East Herzegovinian dialect, due to its origin) is also spoken over large areas, but the key role was played by the fact that the dialect of Dubrovnik, a kind of Croatian Florence, was (i)jekavian and that the old Dubrovnik literature was written in (i)jekavian Štokavian, as well as many old Croatian grammars and dictionaries. A crucial role in the standardization of (i)jekavian Štokavian was played by the influential Serbian linguist Vuk Stefanović Karadžić (1787–1864), whose native rural dialect was ijekavian, but who chose ijekavian as the standard – under the direct guidance of the Slovenian Slavicist Jernej Kopitar (1780–1844) – not because the local dialect of his village was ijekavian (as is often thought), but because of (i)jekavian dialect of Dubrovnik, its renowned literature, and many old Croatian dictionaries Vuk used while writing his famous dictionary (1818). Štokavian in general was more unified in some aspects than might otherwise be expected partly due to post-Ottoman migrations. One more reason for the partial uniformity of literary Štokavian was in the fact that cultural lexicon, mostly in the 19th century, often circulated from Croatian sources to Serbian ones and vice-versa. For example, let us take today completely ordinary Croatian and Serbian words such as *kišobran* ‘umbrella’, *r(j)ječnik* ‘dictionary’, and *predmet* ‘object’. The word *kišobran* first appeared in Croatian *Ilirske narodne novine* (Illyrian National Newspaper) in 1837 and multiple times in other Croatian sources (including the Mažuranić-Užarević’s dictionary from

terms) post-Yugoslav countries (Bosnia & Herzegovina, Croatia, Montenegro, Serbia), which are quite distinct in different countries due to various historical and material circumstances.

Yugoslavia and its breakup

During the period of socialist Yugoslavia, the major official language of the state, and the national language of the mentioned central Yugoslavian republics, was usually called Serbo-Croatian in English. In the language itself, the situation was a bit more complicated and a number of similar terms were used – *hrvatskosrpski* (‘Croato-Serbian’), *srpskohrvatski* (‘Serbo-Croatian’), *hrvatski ili srpski* (‘Croatian or Serbian’), *srpski ili hrvatski* (‘Serbian or Croatian’), etc. The names with the Serbian part first were the most common not only outside of Yugoslavia but also in all republics in Yugoslavia except in Croatia.⁴ Even then, the name was politically sensitive, as can be illustrated by the curious name of the famous Brozović & Ivić (1988) book, *Jezik, srpskohrvatski/hrvatskosrpski, hrvatski ili srpski*, which can literally be translated as ‘Language, Serbo-Croatian/Croato-Serbian, Croatian

1842), while in Serbian, it is attested only in 1856. The word *rječnik*, on the other hand, appears in Croatian sources as early as the 18th century (including two 18th century dictionaries – cf. ARj), whereas in Serbian, it first appears in the title of Vuk’s dictionary from 1818 (although the word itself does not appear in the dictionary). On the other hand, the Russian loanword *predmet* is first attested, like many other Russian loanwords, by the Serbian author Dositej Obradović in 1793, whereas in Croatian sources it appears for the first time in 1835. An even more interesting example is the word *pozorište* ‘theater’ (which is used today only in Serbian, Bosnian, and Montenegrin, while Croatian uses *kazalište*) – *pozorište* was first attested by the Croatian poet from Split, Jerolim Kavanjin (in the early 18th century), next by the Dubrovnik lexicographer Joakim Stulli (1806), thus again in a Croatian source, and only then by the Serbian journalist D. Davidović in 1834, by Vuk in 1843, later in Croatian Šulek’s dictionary (1860), by the Croatian writer Mihovil Pavlinović in 1871, and finally in Popović’s Serbian-German dictionary in 1895 (all according to ARj).

⁴ However, it has to be said that these two-part names (which were long and somewhat clumsy) were often used only officially and not so much in spoken language and unofficial usage. The names Croato-Serbian/Serbo-Croatian were of academic origin and were never really in everyday use everywhere – for instance, the unofficial name of the language in Croatia seems to have been *hrvatski* (Croatian), even before 1990.

or Serbian'. As one can see, the order of the name parts was very important – on the other hand, the national names of Montenegrin and Bosnian Muslim (soon to be Bosniak) speakers (though each with their specific problems) were completely ignored in the official name of the language. Nowadays, the nationalist political and linguist elites often present the socialist Yugoslavian times as completely unitarist in terms of language, but the real situation was more complex. For instance, during AVNOJ (Anti-Fascist Council for the National Liberation of Yugoslavia) in World War II, Croatian and Serbian were treated as separate languages with official documents issued in both. Likewise, in 1974, a new constitution of the Socialist Republic of Croatia was enacted, which in article 138 said: *U Socijalističkoj Republici Hrvatskoj u javnoj je upotrebi hrvatski književni jezik – standardni oblik narodnog jezika Hrvata i Srba u Hrvatskoj, koji se naziva hrvatski ili srpski.* ('In the Socialist Republic of Croatia Croatian literary language is in public use – the standard variety of the vernacular of Croats and Serbs in Croatia, called Croatian or Serbian.') Thus, while e.g. the name of Težak & Babić 1971 grammar was *Pregled gramatike hrvatskosrpskog jezika* ('The overview of the grammar of Croato-Serbian language'), PGHKJ in 1979 was, in line with the new constitution, called *Priručna gramatika hrvatskoga književnog jezika* ('The reference grammar of the Croatian literary language'). This is quite at odds with the simplified picture that both Croatian nationalists but also some Croatian liberals often try to present today – the first claiming that it was impossible at all times to use the name Croatian without Serbian in socialist Yugoslavia, and the second sometimes claiming that separatist names were a strictly post-1990 phenomenon. Another interesting example from the Serbian side is *Institut za srpski jezik SANU* ('The institute for Serbian language SANU'⁵), founded in 1947, which changed its name to *Institut za srpskohrvatski jezik SANU* ('The institute for Serbo-Croatian language SANU') only in 1958 (the exclusive Serbian name came back in 1992).

In reality, despite some attempts, there was never a unified Serbo-Croatian/Croato-Serbian language, i.e. one could never write in both Standard Serbian and Standard Croatian at the same time⁶ – just like

⁵ SANU = *Srpska akademija nauka i umetnosti* ('The Serbian Academy of Sciences and Arts').

⁶ When it comes to non-standard language use, the situation is a bit trickier. While

one cannot write in both British and American English at the same time. In socialist Yugoslavia, the terms often used for Serbian Serbo-Croatian and Croatian Serbo-Croatian were *istočna varijanta* ('the eastern variant') and *zapadna varijanta* ('the western variant') respectively. These were the two main variants, based in Belgrade and Zagreb. The Bosnian and Montenegrin version of the standard also had some specific features, but were less discussed explicitly and marginalized⁷ – just like in politics many things were shaped in the relations of the two biggest nations/nationalisms.

After the breakup of Yugoslavia, as is widely known, four different separate standard varieties were officially adopted – Croatian, Bosnian, Serbian and Montenegrin – each with its own dynamics and different timelines. All of them now have their own separate written grammars, orthographies and dictionaries (only Montenegrin does not have a dictionary), while all four are still based on Neo-Štokavian⁸ – Ijekavian (e.g.

Standard Croatian and Standard Serbian have obvious differences between them (see a bit below for some examples), whether something is nowadays declared a Croatian or a Serbian dialect (or any kind of colloquial variety) depends primarily on non-linguistic factors – the nationality/ethnicity of the speaker or the country where the dialect is spoken. For instance, the language of a rural Ijekavian Štokavian Orthodox speaker from Croatia can be deemed Serbian only because of their ethnicity. In everyday language, people often loosely use the ethnic names in a kind of regional way (similar to the way *dalmatinski* 'Dalmatian' or *istarski* 'Istrian' would be used in Croatia) – e.g. somebody's language will be called *hrvatski* (Croatian) if the speaker sounds as somebody from Croatia (irrespective of their ethnicity, which may be unknown), *srpski* (Serbian) if the speaker sounds as somebody from Serbia, *bosanski* (Bosnian) if the speaker sounds as somebody from Bosnia & Herzegovina (no matter whether the speaker is actually a Bosniak, Croat or Serb from B&H) and *crnogorski* (Montenegrin) if the speaker sounds as somebody from Montenegro (irrespective of how that speaker self-identifies ethnically).

⁷ Cf. Čirgić (2011: 44–45; 192–197) for the language situation in Montenegro in SFRY concerning the "Montenegrin literary-language sub-variant, i.e. a sub-variant of the Serbian variant of 'Serbo-Croatian language'" (: 195–196). In Hodžić (2023), a useful account of the situation in Bosnia & Herzegovina concerning language policy and *bosanskohercegovački standardnojezički izraz* ('Bosnian-Herzegovinian standard-language variety') since the 1970's is given.

⁸ Neo-Štokavian primarily refers to Neo-Štokavian accent (which has a falling and rising toneme, both short and long, with the tone distinction originating in stress retraction) – e.g. Neo-Štokavian/standard *lòpata* 'shovel' (short rising accent) and not the older/dialectal *lopàta* (short falling accent), *lètī* 'flies' (short rising accent)

svijet ‘world’)⁹ in the case of Bosnian, Croatian and Montenegrin¹⁰ and primarily Ekavian (e.g. *svet* ‘world’) in the case of Serbian.¹¹

Contrary to popular belief, the language usage has not really changed significantly in relation to pre-1990 situation, at least when we consider Bosnian, Croatian and Serbian, although primarily Bosnian

and posttonic length) instead of the older/dialectal *letĩ* (Croatia, less so in Bosnia – the so-called “neo-acute” old rising accent) or *letĩ* (Montenegro, Serbia – the long falling accent in old position) – and to a few other features, such as the “new” case endings in plural, e.g. dative/locative/instrumental plural like *vòdama* ‘waters’ (instead of older/dialectal *vodam/vodah/vodami* respectively), although dialectal Neo-Štokavian was (at least not until recently) not really uniform with regards to this (it also exhibited numerous remnants of archaic case ending, e.g. *po vinogradije* ‘in the vineyards’ – cf. Brozović & Ivić (1988: 59)). However, the accentual standardization was always more of an “ideal” than reality – only Bosnia & Herzegovina is dominantly Neo-Štokavian in reality. In the other three countries, a lot of people do not speak according to official prescriptions – e.g. in Croatia the urban dialect of Zagreb and Rijeka has a stress accent, regularly heard in public speech (cf. Kapović, 2018: 339–341); Belgrade itself is in a process of shift from the older Neo-Štokavian pitch-accent system to a newer stress system, while the urban dialect of Niš has had the stress accent for centuries (cf. also Kapović, 2023a: 245–249). In Montenegro, the south-east of the country, which includes almost all larger cities – Podgorica (the capital), Cetinje, Budva, Bar – is Old Štokavian (e.g. *lopàta* and *letĩ*), and this type of accentuation features very prominently in public. This type of accentuation for Standard Montenegrin is currently in the process of standardization (as a parallel variant, together with Neo-Štokavian), which will set Montenegrin accentually apart from the other Štokavian standards.

⁹ Ijekavian (or sometimes Jekavian) means that in a specific set of words the sequence *ije* or *je* is typically found in some Štokavian varieties, while Ekavian means that *e* is found in the same words in other varieties – e.g. *vrijeme/vreme* ‘time, weather’, *cvijet/cvet* ‘flower’, *lijep/lep* ‘beautiful’, *pjevati/pevati* ‘to sing’, *mjeram/mera* ‘measure’, *vjera/vera* ‘faith’, etc.

¹⁰ A word of caution is due here – though the Vukovian writing of the so-called long reflex of jat (<ije>) is used in all three countries, this is phonetically realistic only in Montenegro, where orthographic <ije> is indeed phonetically disyllabic [i.(i) e], while in Croatia and Bosnia & Herzegovina the usual pronunciation is the monosyllabic [je:], thus Montenegrin *svìjet* but Croatian/Bosnian <svijet> [svjèt] (cf. Kapović, 2023a: 183–208 for details now).

¹¹ The Serbian standard is officially also Ijekavian not only in Bosnia & Herzegovina, Montenegro and Croatia (in Bosnia & Herzegovina all Serbs are Ijekavians, while in Croatia most of them are – except for some in the Croatian far east) but also in Serbia itself (the south-west of Serbia is originally Ijekavian), but in reality only Ekavian functions as the standard in Serbia (for instance, Ijekavian speakers regularly shift to Ekavian when moving to Belgrade).

and Croatian each exhibited some changes in their official standards – e.g. lexical changes like Croatian *putovnica* ‘passport’ instead of *pa-soš* (some of these were actually changes of official state terminology, which was then reflected in everyday language) or Bosnian *lahko* ‘easily’ instead of *lako*. The changes were potentially the greatest in Montenegrin, where the “new” written forms like *đed* ‘grandfather’ (and other such words with the so-called third jotation¹² and the phonemes *ś*, *ź*) were codified, but this is not such a major change as it might look at the first glance for a couple of reasons – first of all, such forms have been normal for a long time in Montenegro in spontaneous spoken language (which was known even outside Montenegro); secondly, such “new” written forms are variant and not obligatory (forms like *djed* etc. are still standard as well¹³); and thirdly, the new Montenegrin orthography still has to achieve widespread popularity in Montenegro.

While some language changes did occur, they were predominantly political and symbolic in nature – and the question of language names is indeed by itself often more a political than linguistic question. Language policies have simply followed changes that occurred in politics in general. Prior to 1990, the Štokavian standard was mostly conceived, in harmony with the official political ideology of socialist Yugoslavia, as one polycentric language, while after 1990 various varieties of this polycentric language came to be regarded as separate, but very similar, standard varieties.¹⁴

¹² In Montenegro, the changes *tj > ć*, *cj > č*, *dj > đ*, *sj > ś*, *zj > ź* are typical for all the dialects and are now also present in the standard variety as well. The phonemes *ć*, *đ*, of course, exist from before in the language, and *ś* and *ź* also appear in some cases from other sources, for instance in nicknames like *Mašo*, *Pušo* (such words actually confirm the phonemicity of [e] and [z] in Montenegrin), cf. Čirgić (2011: 163, 170–171).

¹³ Writing *đed* ‘grandfather’, *đevojka* ‘girl’ or *ćerati* ‘to force, drive’ etc. is hardly new in fact (unlike writing *ś* and *ź*), since this was the way Vuk himself wrote in the first edition of his dictionary. Vuk only started writing *djed*, *djevojka*, *tjerati* etc. in later editions.

¹⁴ Wet dreams of some nationalists that these new separate languages will with time quickly differentiate have not come true, especially considering new technology – cf. Kapović (2020: 176).

It's all nationalism

Post-Yugoslav area has often been criticized for its nationalist politics (starting with Milošević's Greater Serbia expansionism) which led to numerous wars. Nationalism is, likewise, obviously reflected in language as well and all language and symbolic changes are obviously also rooted in nationalism – it is quite clear that the breakup of the common state also led to the symbolic breakup of the common language. However, while some foreign linguists will all too easily disparage the rampant nationalism in the region, there is some nuance to be added here, which is often not understood in a proper manner – because not all post-Yugoslav standard-language changes were necessarily just invented out of thin air by nationalistic standardologists (some were but not all) and because there was never simply any neutral, non-nationalist and scientifically correct starting point that was only later superseded by absurd nationalist and political interventions in language.

Like it or not, the whole thing was through and through nationalist from the start – with Serbo-Croatian being as nationalist a project as separate Serbian, Croatian, Bosnian and Montenegrin are. The only difference is that Serbo-Croatian (or whatever it was called in its older variants – e.g. Yugoslavian, Illyrian, Slovincic, etc.) is nationalist from a wider, unitarist perspective, while Serbian, Croatian, Bosnian and Montenegrin are nationalist in an isolationist sense. But both unitary and separatist nationalisms are still nationalism and Serbo-Croatian as one polycentric language cannot be regarded, as it often implicitly is (not only abroad but also by some liberals in ex-Yugoslavia as well), as some anti-nationalist neutral position with clear scholarly validation. The thing is – the standard variety is not the only language variety that exists and standard varieties do not exist in vacuum. They occupy, as a superregional form of communication, not just areas where dialects similar to the standard variety is spoken (i.e. Neo-Štokavian dialects when it comes to the BCMS complex) but often also dialects that are much more diverse than the standard variety (i.e. Old Štokavian, Čakavian, Kajkavian and Torlak when it comes to BCMS). Dialectologically speaking, there is no such thing as Serbo-Croatian because there is no sharp language border on the national/state borders between neither Croatia and Slovenia in the north-west, nor between Serbia and Bul-

garia in the south-east. The whole South Slavic language area, from Bulgaria to Slovenia, is a dialectal continuum, with sharp dialectal borders only in cases of later (post-Ottoman) migrational dialects. While it is completely correct to note that there are no sharp language/dialectal boundaries between Croatia, Bosnia & Herzegovina, Montenegro and Serbia – one should also note that there is no real language border on the outskirts of the “Bosnian/Croatian/Montenegrin/Serbian” complex. In Croatia, western Neo-Štokavian dialects make a natural continuation of southern Čakavian (which can be seen clearly e.g. on the Pelješac peninsula or in the Poljice region), western Slavonian Old Štokavian dialect make a natural continuation to Kajkavian (nowadays obfuscated by later migrations), while northern Čakavian and Kajkavian transition rather smoothly to Slovene dialects.¹⁵ Likewise, Štokavian dialects in Serbia smoothly transition to Torlak dialects, which in turn represent a transition to Bulgarian/Macedonian dialects – Torlak famously, just like Bulgarian, has a free stress accent with no distinctive length and tones, has lost most nominal morphology, has no infinitive and has postpositional definite article.

On the other hand, one should also not naively think, as some well-meaning people sometimes do, that confessional/political differences cannot also produce or be in line with certain language/dialectal differences. For instance, only Catholics/Croats and Muslims/Bosniaks can be Old Štokavian and Ikavian speakers in Bosnia & Herzegovina, while the Orthodox/Serbs are always and only Neo-Štokavian and Ijekavian speakers. Similarly, for Muslims it is also typical to preserve the phoneme *h* better (which is then reflected in the current Bosnian standard¹⁶) and to lose the *č* : *ć* opposition. An interesting example are also Montenegrin Muslims in Podgorica and Gusinje, who have/had the Ikavian reflex of the old long jat (*svit* ‘world’) (Čirgić, 2007: 60–73; Čirgić, 2020: 44), unlike the more usual Ijekavian reflex (*svijet*). Likewise, certain areas, which may loosely correspond to later national/ethnic borders can have certain language traits in common. This is, for instance, the case with Western Štokavian dialectal traits that it has in common with Čakavian and Kajkavian (though most of these

¹⁵ The transitional nature is most clear in the case of Kajkavian – cf. Kapović (2017).

¹⁶ Cf. e.g. an interesting note in Hodžić (2023: 31⁵–32⁵) on *aždaha* ‘monster’ and *promaha* ‘draft’.

have not found way into the Croatian standard), e.g. *meja* ‘border’ instead of *međa*, preservation of old accentuation (e.g. the neo-acute but also the appearance of certain innovative accentual traits (cf. Kapović, 2015: 633–638)), $e > a$ after palatals as in *jačmen(ac)* ‘stye’ instead of *ječmen(ac)*, etc. Somewhat similar to that, Montenegrin dialects, both Neo-Štokavian (of the *lòpata* type) and Old Štokavian (of the *lopàta* type) have some common traits (cf. Čirgić, 2020: 11–27) – e.g. the third jotation (*ćeram* ‘I force’, *đeca* ‘children’, *šekira* ‘axe’, *izelica* ‘glutton’ instead of *tjeram*, *djeca*, *sjekira*, *izjelica*), phonemic *ś* [ɛ] and *ž* [z], and the “acute posttonic length” (*pàzīti* ‘to watch out’, *ćèrāti* ‘to force’, *krāvāma* ‘with the cows’ instead of *pāzīti*, *tjērāti*, *krāvāma* (cf. Kapović, 2015: 516–525; Kapović, 2022: 292–294)).

Not so special

Although quite popular in sociolinguistic literature and scholarly treatises of language and nationalism, the case of former Yugoslavia and Serbo-Croatian “disintegrating” into Bosnian, Croatian, Montenegrin and Serbian is actually not that special. The difference between different standard Štokavian varieties is very similar to various varieties of English, Spanish or French, the only difference being that the latter varieties are a product of colonialism which is not the case with Štokavian. Thus, a comparison with German (spoken in Germany, Austria and Switzerland) or Dutch (in the Netherlands and in Belgium) varieties is more apt. Outside of Europe, the situation is comparable with Indonesian in Indonesia and Malay(sian) in Malaysia, Persian/Farsi in Iran, Dari in Afghanistan and Tajiki in Tajikistan, or with Hindi in India and Urdu in Pakistan¹⁷. The last case is very similar to the Croatian and

¹⁷ Kordić (2024: 168) claims that the “[d]ifference in the standard language of Bosniaks, Croats, Montenegrins and Serbs are less significant than those between the variants of German, English, Dutch or Hindi-Urdu”. This claim is very suspicious (and the references cited which are supposed to confirm the claim are equally unconvincing), but even if that were true that does not really change much in the argument. The same is true of her reference which claims that B/C/M/S mutual intelligibility is greater than the one between the standard variants of English, French, German and Spanish (especially considering her practice of “reference padding” her texts in order to prove her point). It is, however, interesting to note that for all the language nationalism in former Yugoslavia, nobody has ever bothe-

Serbian one – cf. the difference of the script, religion and cultural influences (Cf. Kapović, 2020: 181³⁴). These cases differ in how political the question of language is and how symbolically important the question of name(s) is – as can be seen, in some cases (primarily the colonial ones but not exclusively), the same name is used, while in others different names exist, although that does not always imply that naming is necessarily a politically hot topic.

Possibilities and counterfactuals

Language names, just like national names, are always a question of politics and identity. One can be in favor of one nation and one language on a territory, of ten nations and ten languages on a territory, of ten nations and one language (or even of one nation and ten languages), but in the end this is always necessarily a political stance. And these claims and ideas can change over time. Let us illustrate this with examples from ex-Yugoslavia. An obvious political fact is, as is currently the case, that there are a number of different nation(alitie)s (Bosnian, Croatian, Montenegrin, Serbian...) in former Yugoslavia, each having its own standard language. On the other hand, one could also claim – as some people claimed in the past – that all South Slavs (with or without the Slovenes, Bulgarians and Macedonians) speak one language, whether one calls it (as it has been called) Illyrian, Yugoslav

red (because it would probably have to involve a collaboration of the two sides) to write a serious treatment of language differences between e.g. Standard Croatian and Standard Serbian, although there are quite enough of them even without any kind of artificial interventions (just like one can find a number of differences between American and British English) – e.g. lexically Croatian *kino* ‘movie theater’, *leća* ‘lentil’, *tvornica* ‘factory’, *umjetan* ‘artificial’, *vlak* ‘train’ ~ Serbian *bioskop*, *sočivo*, *fabrika*, *veštački*, *voz* respectively. Of course, that does not imply that Croatian and Serbian are not mutually completely intelligible, which they most certainly are and nobody would deny that – not even the most fervent nationalists. However, one also has to acknowledge that approximately the same amount of differences that exist between Standard Croatian and Standard Serbian can be found between e.g. the modern urban local dialects of Split and Zagreb (if one takes into account the most archaic local varieties only, the differences are even more pronounced) – e.g. Split *botun* ‘button’, *kapula* ‘red onion’, *lavandin* ‘sink’, *patike* ‘sneakers’, *poma* ‘tomato’ ~ Zagreb *gumb*, *luk*, *lavabo*, *tenisice*, *paradajz* respectively (cf. also Osijek *dugme*, *luk*, *lavabo*, *patike*, *paradajz* and Pula *dugme*, *luk*, *lavandin*, *patike*, *paradajz* – Standard Croatian words would be *puce/dugme*, *luk*, *umivaonik*, *tenisice*, *rajčica*, but local words are often used in public as well).

or Serbo-Croatian, and that they are one people. One can also claim politically, as is done by the signatories of the recent *Declaration on the common language* (2017), that different nations (Bosnian, Croatian, Montenegrin, Serbian) speak one language. We can apply the same kind of logic a level below, within modern nation-states. For instance, one can claim politically that in Croatia there is only one (main) nation and one language (this is the current dominant and official ideology, of course). But one can also claim, though such claims are nowadays on the political margins, that ethnic Croats actually speak three languages (Štokavian, Čakavian and Kajkavian), or that these are even three separate nations¹⁸. Likewise, while in modern times the equivalence of Bosniak, Croatian and Serbian nation with their respective religions – Muslim, Catholic and Orthodox (the Montenegrins do not fit in clearly in this regard) – is well-established in wide perception, this was not necessarily the case in the past and there were concepts such as Catholic Serbs, Muslim Croats, etc.¹⁹ In short – all kinds of political claims on nations (and similarly on languages) are theoretically possible. Since there are no “objective nations”, it is impossible to make neutral, non-ideological claims in this regard – one can only describe the identities that actually exist and examine and analyze them critically.

One could think that a situation would necessarily be different in case where one does not deal with a dialectal continuum but with sharp language borders – e.g. Basque amongst Spanish and French – but that is not actually true. While it is true that Basque is completely different from Spanish and French in a way that is completely unlike the distinction of e.g. Galician to Spanish and Portuguese, the political-language situation that we find today is not the only one that could have emerged. For instance, in different historical circumstances, there could have been more than one Basque nation and Basque dialects could have been regarded politically as separate (if close) languages. Also, some speakers of Basque could, for example, regard themselves as French in

¹⁸ In modern Croatia, there is a minority of activists who advocate the idea of Čakavian and Kajkavian as separate languages. This is, of course, a legitimate political idea, but it is also a fact that different Čakavian and Kajkavian local dialects can be very diverse not only structurally but also genetically (e.g. the southern Čakavian dialect of Lastovo and the northern Čakavian dialect of Buzet), that there are often no firm dialect borders and that ideas of unified “Čakavian” and “Kajkavian” are not much more realistic dialectologically than are clearly political ideas of “Croatian” or “Serbo-Croatian”.

¹⁹ Nowadays, such concepts exist only on the political (and individual) fringes.

spite of their language – compare that, for instance, with some speakers of Pontic Greek that are Muslims and regards themselves nationally as Turks in modern times (while others are still Orthodox and consider themselves Greeks²⁰).

Counterfactuals are obviously possible in all cases and it is important to always have this in mind when discussing problems of language and nationalism. Let us mention just two more. Today, it is taken as a sociolinguistic and political fact that there is only one Arabic language, while there is a wide array of Slavic (standard) languages. However, while there is indeed one standard Arabic language – Modern Standard Arabic (MSA) – which is a sort of modernized version of Classical (Quranic) Arabic, in reality Arabic has some 30 regional varieties (such as Moroccan Arabic, Tunisian Arabic, Levantine Arabic, Hijazi, etc.). These are as different structurally as modern Slavic languages are, often completely mutually unintelligible and could be, and sometimes are, regarded as completely different languages. The reason why they are commonly regarded as one language is them having the same standard variety due to obvious political, historical, cultural and religious reasons. The only exception is Maltese because it is spoken by non-Muslims and culturally/politically in Europe – otherwise it could be treated as one more regional variety of Arabic. Now imagine an alternate-reality pan-Slavic standard variety, which would encompass all Slavia. In different historical circumstances, it is not unimaginable that modern Slavic languages would be considered just dialects, while sharing some kind of modernized Old Church Slavic as basis of their common pan-Slavic standard. What is more, while Quran stems from the 7th century, Old Church Slavic is even more recent – from the 9th century. It has obviously not turned out that way, but if people like Juraj Križanić (1618–1683), who championed a pan-Slavic literary language and Christian unity, had gotten their way, it might have been different.

²⁰ Of course, both Turks and Greeks are modern national identities – as all nations are. Cf. an anecdote told in Kaldellis (2008: 42–43), where the inhabitants of the island of Lemnos still considered themselves as Romans (and not Helenes/Greeks) in 1912 as a remnant of the Roman identity of the former (Eastern) Roman Empire (widely known by its ahistorical misnomer Byzantium).

Types of language nationalism

While one can speak of political and language nationalism in all the countries in question (Bosnia & Herzegovina, Croatia, Montenegro, Serbia), these nationalisms can be quite different in some regards. The main difference is that Serbian language-nationalism is mostly expansionist (“everybody speaks Serbian”), while Bosnian, Croatian and Montenegrin language-nationalisms are mostly separatist (“Bosnian/Croatian/Montenegrin is a separate language, different from Serbian”).

Serbian (language) nationalism has been dominantly expansionist (“everybody is actually Serbian and everybody speaks Serbian”) already since the 19th century – from the notorious *Načertanije* (1844) on. It is quite easy to understand why that is so, without succumbing to nationalist paranoia, chauvinism and conspiracy theories. Serbia was, with the exception of the smaller Montenegro, the first modern South Slavic independent state. It is also the largest South Slavic nation (not counting Bulgarians), which has since its nationalist inception in the 19th century tried to encompass primarily all Orthodox South Slavs (except for Bulgarians – and Macedonians in modern times) and to widen its power in relation first to the Ottoman Empire, then Austria-Hungary (when it comes to Bosnian & Herzegovina) and in the 20th century to more western South Slavic countries (via Serbian domination in Yugoslavian monarchy and through war aggression after the breakup of socialist Yugoslavia). Today, almost all Orthodox, or originally Orthodox, South Slavs in Croatia and Bosnia & Herzegovina consider themselves ethnically Serb and this is also true for approximately half of the Orthodox population in modern Montenegro²¹. All of this – early statehood, being the largest nation in Yugoslavia (with the capital in Belgrade in Serbia) and presence of Orthodox Štokavian-speaking population in all central Yugoslavian countries – together with the political and economic elites that wanted more power by using the greater Serbia nationalism²², ensured the material circumstances for the presence of expansionist nationalism in Serbia. The position of Serbia as the largest country and

²¹ Serbian Orthodox Church has had and still has a major role in promoting Serbian nationalism not only in Montenegro but elsewhere as well.

²² In the first Yugoslavia, the nationalism of the Serbian bourgeoisie was routinely condemned by the Communist party as well.

population in Yugoslavia also influences other policies – for instance, Serbian language politics tends to be more “liberal” and anti-purist (in the sense of easily accepting foreign words, including Croatian ones), typical of many big languages such as Russian or English (while e.g. Croatian language policies tend to be more purist, similar to language policies of smaller languages like Icelandic).

The position of the biggest nation also enabled Serbian nationalism to be “inclusive” in an imperialist fashion (e.g. various Štokavian varieties treated as “different types of Serbian”) and to feel quite “secure” – in opposition to other (language) nationalisms, which are characterized by the constant feeling of vulnerability (whether the feeling is realistic or not).²³ After the breakup of Yugoslavia, Serbian language nationalism felt confused for some time, because it was not clear which course it should take – maintaining the Serb-nationalist expansionist vision of Serbo-Croatian or taking clue from other nations and switching to simply Serbian (which can be conceived as either expansionist or separatist). From the 1990’s up until recently, greater-Serbian nationalism when it comes to language was usually limited to regular but mostly isolated individual excesses. However, this changes from the beginning of 2020’s, with a seemingly new political currents coming from above, surely related to Aleksandar Vučić’s regime and the policies of *srpski svet* (‘Serbian world’). The crucial role in the new expansionist Serbian language nationalism was played by a number of the so-called annual “interdepartmental Serbist declarations” (*interkatedarske srbističke deklaracije*) from 2020 until 2023. In these declarations, indicatively signed by all faculties, institutes and departments of Serbian language and literature, Bosnian, Croatian and Montenegrin are basically interpreted as being “actually” Serbian and, likewise, as one may also imagine it, Bosniaks, Croats and Montenegrins are also likely to be Serbs “in denial”. This has, quite predictably, triggered numerous, sometimes also fiercely nationalist, responses from the other countries – especially from Croatia – and has caused great damage for any kind of future collaboration of e.g. Croatian and Serbian linguists.

²³ Although Serbian nationalism also uses the ideologeme of *ugroženost* (‘endangerment’) profusely in case of Serbs outside of Serbia, e.g. in Croatia or on Kosovo.

Croatian (language) nationalism is today primarily isolationist (“Croatian is not the same as Serbian”²⁴), while still trying to incorporate all South Slavic Catholics (except Slovenes) as Croats and their dialects as part of Croatian language – including such diverse cases as Janjevo in Kosovo, Karaševo in Romania and the coastal part of Montenegro (e.g. Catholics/Croats in the Bay of Kotor or in the Bar region) – which can be regarded as expansionist. In the past, expansionism was at times much more pronounced within certain strains of Croatian nationalism.²⁵ However, the material preconditions for Croatian expansionist nationalism are not very encouraging – Croats represent a sizable population only in Bosnia & Herzegovina (but even there they are the smallest of the three constitutional nations), while their numbers in Serbia and Montenegro are rather small. Croatian language politics is typically and traditionally purist²⁶, typical usually for smaller languages (such as Slovene) but also some bigger languages (such as Turkish), and seeks differentiation from other Štokavian varieties – whether they be real (e.g. via insistence on Western Štokavian – though this is in reality often not reflected in the standard Croatian variety) or not. An interesting example of Croatian separatist language nationalism is insistence by some Croatian linguists that the orthographic <ije>, a reflex of the old long jat (Common Slavic *ě), is actually a diphthong [je], which would mean that Croatian has six phonemic vowels (as opposed to Serbian five vowels). The problem is, however, that this “phantom diphthong” does not really exist and that it is pronounced as a simple [je:] in Modern Croatian (Cf. Kapović, 2023a: 202–207), as already mentioned.

Bosniak (language) nationalism primarily promotes Bosnian language as the language of all Bosniaks in Bosnia & Herzegovina, including the inhabitants of Herzegovina, and potentially all inhabitants of Bosnia and Herzegovina regardless of religion/ethnicity (Cf. e.g. Greenberg, 2021: 32–33). Bosniak nationalism is primarily isolationist (“Bosnian as a distinct language compared to other Štokavian languages”), although one could interpret as expansionist its tendency to

²⁴ Likewise, “Croats are not Serbs” (and not e.g. “all Serbs are actually Croat”).

²⁵ For instance, the extreme Ustaša Croatian nationalism in World War 2 was not only expansionist but also openly genocidal.

²⁶ This has started to change slowly with advance of the modern anti-prescriptivist current in Croatian linguistics, cf. e.g. Starčević, Kapović & Sarić (2023).

encompass all Slavic dialects spoken by Muslims in former Yugoslavia. According to this conception, Bosniaks who speak Bosnian would not only include Štokavian speaking Muslim Bosnians and Herzegovinians, but also Muslim Štokavian speakers in Sandžak in Serbia, Muslim Štokavians in Montenegro, and even Goran(c)i in Kosovo/Albania/Macedonia (Muslim Torlak speakers (cf. Długosz, 2023)). Bosniak (and to a lesser extent Bosnian-language) nationalism can also be considered expansionist in regards to its modern relation to the Croats in Bosnia & Herzegovina (the voting problem in the Federation part of Bosnia & Herzegovina), while the same can be said for Croatian meddling into Bosnia & Herzegovina from the 1990's wars onwards. Bosnian language-nationalism pays special tribute to its Islamic heritage by its proneness to stress Bosnian Oriental (Turkish, Arabic, Persian) vocabulary.

Montenegrin nationalism is quite distinct from the previous three and is the most progressive (liberal and occasionally even left-leaning) of the four. It is primarily isolationist (“Montenegrins are not Serbs” and “Montenegrin is not Serbian”) and tries to affirm Montenegrin characteristics (such as the realistic Montenegrin pronunciation such as *ǰe* ‘where’ or *śeme* ‘seed’ instead of *gdje* or *sjeme*), while at the same time espousing realistic and not prescriptivist and artificial view on language – more on that further on in the paper. Montenegrin nationalism is the only of the four major nationalisms we are discussing here that is still not fully formed and is enduring great pressure from expansionist Serbian nationalism. If one would want to give linguistic parallels, the position of Montenegrin (language) nationalism in relation to Serbian (language) nationalism can be compared with the position of Macedonian (language) nationalism in opposition to Bulgarian (language) nationalism (the difference being in the fact that a separate Macedonian standard is much older and well-established). Also, the situation with the “neo-Montenegrin” standardization, with *ǰe*, *śeme*, *izelica* etc., in opposition to a more Serbian-like and classical standardization, can be to a point compared with the Norwegian dichotomy of Nynorsk and Bokmål.

From liberal antinationalism to (unintentional) covert Serbian nationalism

Nationalist excesses in former Yugoslavia, in language and outside of it, have provoked various reactions. In language, perhaps the strongest one was the already mentioned *Declaration on the common language* (2017), where thousands of intellectuals from former Yugoslavia signed a declaration that they speak one common language (without a specified name). While it undoubtedly espoused numerous positive ideas (such as the legitimate critique of nationalism in general, prescriptivism, artificial nationalist interventions into language, etc.), it also had some problems – it was written as a supposedly neutral and non-political document (which is obviously not the case), it isolates nationalism in language from broader issues of nationalism as if the two can be treated separately²⁷, and parts of it were worded in a scholarly disingenuous way, e.g. by mentioning only pluricentric languages with one name like English, German or French, while disregarding languages like Hindi/Urdu, Malay(sian)/Indonesian, etc., which do not fit the agenda²⁸. In the end, the Declaration makes a tactical (“realistic”) choice of trying to deconstruct only language nationalism and not nationalism in general – as if language nationalism was somehow more artificial than general political nationalism, even though separate languages are just as much ideological constructs²⁹ as separate nations are. What is even more pro-

²⁷ E.g. ethnically based school programs do not exist because of language only as it is implied and it would exist even if everybody would accept only one name for the former Serbo-Croatian – just like it does in North Ireland although everybody there speaks English now. Likewise, the term “school segregation” itself is problematic because it has the connotation of e.g. former racial segregation in the United States of America, while in former Yugoslavia such separate schools are used in order for minorities (for instance, the Serb minority in Croatia) to be able to realize their minority rights – learning not only in their own language/variety, but e.g. their own national history, literature, culture, etc. This practice is indeed problematic in some regards, to be sure (because it does divide children), but it is something quite different than the mentioned racial segregation and it is often the national minorities themselves (for instance, the Serb, Czech or Italian minority in Croatia) that are the main advocates of such practice.

²⁸ For a more detailed critique, cf. Kapović (2020: 178–181).

²⁹ As noted by Wiese (2023: 3, 7) named languages and their boundaries are not real – they are ideological constructions.

blematic is that its criticism of language nationalism stops at the borders of central republics of former Yugoslavia – somewhat similar to an imaginary deconstruction of (political) nationalism which would claim that separate nationalisms (Bosniak, Croat, Montenegrin, Serb) are false but that the Yugoslav nationalism is somehow the “correct” nationalism.

One other problematic side of the Declaration can also be seen in the stance Snježana Kordić, a sort of a main figure of the Declaration, has concerning the “neo-Montenegrin” standardization³⁰, i.e. primarily the standardization of the new letters/phonemes *ś*, *ž*.³¹ While it is perfectly politically legitimate that Kordić has a political opinion that Montenegro and Serbia should have a more or less uniform standard dialect, it is unclear why the Montenegrins should accept language norms from Belgrade if that is not what they want (some inhabitants of Montenegro are in favor of that, while others are not) or why should they not be allowed to speak and write as they want to? And why shouldn't the Montenegrin standard be in line with the way all Montenegrins actually speak? After all, it is up to the Montenegrins to decide upon that. Kordić is always very concerned with the question of mutual intelligibility, but even this is not really in jeopardy – Montenegrins pronouncing, as they normally do, and/or writing *śećati se* ‘to remember’ or *đevojka* ‘girl’ instead of *s(j)ećati se* or *d(j)evojka* hardly makes them unintelligible to other Štokavian speakers. And last but certainly not least, Jelena Šušanj (2022: 483) is quite right to point out that Kordić, who is otherwise an outspoken critic of prescriptivism, artificial codification of language and a proponent of realistic standard as actually used by the speakers (at least when it comes to Croatia), takes a completely different, inconsistent and hypocritical approach – against the vernacular and the ‘normal everyday language’ – when it comes to Montenegro.

An even more problematic example is the *Glušica 2020*, a book by the Montenegrin (but in fact pro-Serb³²) linguist Rajka Glušica, where

³⁰ Cf. e.g. <https://arhiva.tacno.net/novosti/intervju-snjezana-kordic-nacionalizam-je-jedan-oblik-ludacke-kosulje/>.

³¹ In fact, it is only the letters that are actually new (in standard usage), because the phonemes *ś* and *ž* have been distinctive in Montenegrin vernacular for a long time – the only change now being that their phonemicity is officially recognized in one variant of standard Montenegrin.

³² The whole of Montenegrin population is roughly divided in half into pro-Serb and pro-Montenegrin factions, where the split is not ethnic but ideological – the

the “neo-Montenegrin” language standardization is fiercely denounced as nationalism and strongly opposed (very often on false linguistic grounds), while supposedly “objective” linguistic insights³³ are invoked.³⁴ However, the agenda behind the book is obviously clearly nationalist as well – it is just that the nationalism in question is Serbian rather than Montenegrin³⁵. Again, it is quite legitimate to have different political stances, but it is problematic when a nationalist agenda is masked as the supposed anti-nationalism or “objective” linguistics, even though Glušica is clearly espousing openly prescriptivist and elitist stances. When both sides are nationalist, denouncing nationalism in general will not do – one has to closely analyze which side espouses what kind of nationalism, nationalism of the oppressor or nationalism of the oppressed, and what kind of ideologies go in hand with these nationalisms.³⁶

pro-Serb side is more right-wing, conservative, clerical, anti-LGBT, pro-Russia, anti-minority, pro-Četnik, etc. (Četniks were a far-right Nazi-aligned paramilitary Serbian force in World War 2), while the pro-Montenegrin side is more liberal/progressive, secularist, pro-EU/West/NATO, respects minority rights, antifascist, etc. For the origin of such a division in the early 1990’s cf. Šistek 2015: 168. When it comes to language, the pro-Serb faction is obviously against the “neo-Montenegrin” standardization, while the pro-Montenegrin side is more prone to “neo-Montenegrin” standardization but more when it comes to pronunciation than writing (the classical standard orthography, without the new letters *š*, *ž* and without the third jotation, is still more popular in practice).

³³ Following Kordić 2010 monograph.

³⁴ A thorough and lucid critique of Glušica from a pro-Montenegrin but also anti-prescriptivist (!) perspective can be found in Šušanj (2022).

³⁵ Note here once again that the Serb nationalism in Montenegro is, as a rule, much more right-wing and reactionary, than the generally more liberal and progressive Montenegrin nationalism. The progressiveness of Montenegrin nationalism can now also be seen in anti-prescriptivist stances of pro-Montenegrin linguists and proponents of “neo-Montenegrin” standardization – for that, cf. again Šušanj (2022).

³⁶ Interestingly enough, the stances of Glušica (2020) garnered uncritical and very favorable support from Milorad Pupovac (2022), a linguist from Croatia (who was, besides being a linguist, also the main political representative of the Serb minority in Croatia), with the same kind of supposedly “anti-nationalist” arguments and frequent referencing to modern sociolinguistic literature, while at the same time passionately denouncing Montenegrin vernacular (which hardly goes hand in hand with modern sociolinguistics and critical linguistics) as something unworthy of standardization. For a critique of Pupovac 2022 from the Montenegrin perspective cf. Čirgić (2023) and Vujović (2023).

“Disintegration”, reality, Western smugness and political correctness

Narratives of some sharp “disintegration”, “breakup” of a “joint language”, etc. in 1991, as sometimes presented in works of foreign linguists (e.g. in works like Greenberg, 2004³⁷), are in many regards false – except in the symbolic sense. There was never one, uniform Serbo-Croatian, just like there was never (at least in the last one hundred years or so), one unified English – in the same manner as today one cannot speak/write in both American and British English at the same time (except by artificially mixing the varieties), the same was true of Croatian and Serbian. Neither today nor in 1989, 1909, or in 1879, could one write a somewhat longer text which would be both Croatian and Serbian at the same time. Whether one considers Croatian and Serbian completely different languages (which is obviously not true), very similar but different standard varieties, or varieties of the same polycentric standard, and whether it is 1989 or 2024, does not really change anything crucial – these two varieties were and are different. Not different as Croatian and Hungarian are, or even as Standard Croatian and Standard Slovene are, but different as British and American English or Hindi and Urdu are.

Different language names do not really change the reality – they are, of course, symbolically performative and thus not unimportant, but they do not change the language itself (most of post-1991 language changes were superficial), nor do they impede wider communication and intelligibility. Though people can certainly have differing opinions in such issues, it should not be controversial that every nation has a right to call its language by its own national/ethnic name. Calling a language variety by one’s own national/ethnic name is quite trivial and normal almost everywhere in the world – from Dyrbal and Indonesian to Norwegian. It may not be usual, for historical reasons, in ex-colonialist countries (in Americas and Australia), but Croatian as spoken in Croatia or Montenegrin as spoken in Montenegro are not a product of colonialism. Likewise, the whole world does not have to be molded the way the colonialist West perceives it.

³⁷ Cf. e.g. Greenberg (2018: 25³) who, with seemingly implicit disbelief, says “Internally, within Croatia there was a broad consensus that a separate Croatian language had existed long before 1991”.

Deconstruction of nationalist myths and programs, which are often socially backward and harmful, is without doubt necessary in former Yugoslavia as everywhere, but Western academics (and also post-Yugoslav liberal anti-nationalist scholars) should be careful not to engage in Orientalist (or, more precisely, Balkanist – (cf. Todorova, 2009) smug tropes about “wild Balkan nationalists” and a kind of post-Yugoslav negative exceptionalism, especially when ill-informed (e.g. “look at those funny Montenegrin nationalists with their made-up new letters”). Although former Yugoslavia is unfortunately still riddled with nationalism, with all its problems, complacent denunciations of “primitive Balkan nationalism” just because different peoples use their own ethnic names for their language are hardly appropriate. Especially considering everybody has their own blind spots – for instance, the United States of America are in many regards much more overtly nationalistic than former Yugoslavia, with its unbridled ubiquitous flag waving, national anthems before every basketball game, nationalist tropes like “support our troops” everywhere and veterans regularly appearing before sporting events (which seems ridiculous even in comparison with former Yugoslavia), etc.

While it is immature and unnecessary of post-Yugoslav nationalists to get themselves all worked up over foreign scholars still using the old name Serbo-Croatian in the literature, it must be said that the term is nowadays considered politically incorrect, and for good reasons – if only for the reason that the language in question is not only the language of Serbs and Croats but also, in equal manner, of Bosniaks and Montenegrins. Thus, the now already quite common name Bosnian/Croatian/Montenegrin/Serbian, usually shortened to BCMS (the Montenegrin part should not be excluded, as some still tend to do), is much more appropriate when needed – e.g. when citing that the word for ‘goat’ is *kôza* in all four standard varieties in a paper on historical linguistics. Of course, in some circumstances, separate names will be used, sometimes the name Standard Štokavian may be used, etc. The common international term BCMS (in BCMS literature itself, there is no equivalent since usually only the national names are used) is undoubtedly necessary for usage in linguistic literature (when appropriate) and in academic circles (e.g. one can hardly expect a German or an American university to have courses on four separate varieties) – thus, extremist anger of certain

post-Yugoslav nationalists in that regard is unrealistic and unnecessary. But it also has to be said that the term BCMS is useful only in such academic and scholarly regard. When it comes to “regular” people there seems to be, for instance, absolutely no interest in learning BCMS as a foreign language – foreigners, expatriates or diaspora are not really interested in BCMS as a whole. Usually, everybody wants to learn the variety that is important for them (e.g. Croatian and not BCMS) – whether it is their heritage language, language of their ancestors, of their spouse, of the country they have moved to, and so on.

The curious case of Montenegrin

Not all language nationalisms are the same and they should not all be treated with the same amount of critique. For instance, calling a language by your national/ethnic name (e.g. Montenegrin) and insisting on its really-existing features is hardly the same kind of thing as is expansionist and chauvinist nationalist claims like the ones that “actually everybody speaks Serbian” (and “actually everybody is Serbian”) as made by many Serbian nationalists. We have already mentioned three possible dichotomies when it comes to nationalism – the opposition of the nationalism of the oppressor (e.g. American nationalism in the US) and the nationalism of the oppressed (e.g. Amerindian nationalism(s) in the US), the distinction of a unitarist (e.g. Yugoslav nationalism) and an isolationist nationalism (e.g. Croat nationalism), and the difference between expansionist (e.g. greater-Serbia nationalism) and separatist nationalism (e.g. Montenegrin nationalism). A fourth kind of dichotomy can be introduced when speaking on nationalist language policies – the opposition of nationalist language interventions producing artificial differences and nationalist language interventions affirming/standardizing really-existing language features.

Thus, it is important to distinguish, for example, artificial prescriptivist interventions without basis in current normal usage in Croatian – such as the promotion of words like *šport* instead of *sport* ‘sport’, *pogrješka* instead of *(po)greška* ‘mistake’, *glasovati* instead of *glasati* ‘to vote’, *djelatnik* instead of *radnik* ‘worker’, etc.,³⁸ which were of-

³⁸ Such words can later gain usage in the language due to the interventions themselves. The variant *šport* (which was spontaneously used in parts of Croatia earlier

ten presented as the only “correct” variants – and quite moderate and variant standardization of actually existing general phonological features of spoken language – e.g. *đeca*, *šekira*, *izelica* in Montenegrin. The newly standardized phonemes *ś* and *ź* and the results of the third jotation (like *đed*, *śever* ‘north’, *koži* ‘goat’ – beside the variants *djed*, *sjever*, *koz(i)ji*) have rightly been widely recognized as most iconic in the “neo-Montenegrin” standardization.³⁹ It is also true that these features sharply distinguish the new Montenegrin standard from all other Štokavian standards (Croatian has *djed*, *sjever*, *kozji*, Bosnian has *djed*, *sjever*, *koziji*⁴⁰ and Serbia Serbian has *ded*, *sever*, *koziji*). However, what is often disregarded and misunderstood, even by linguists (who are often not well informed of the realistic state of things in Montenegro), is that all such forms (like *đed*, *śever*, *koži*) are variant (so one can use either them or the older standardized variant *djed*, *sjever*, *koz(i)ji*). While this is true⁴¹, this is not something that is unusual⁴² – what is even more important is, as already said, that these forms are something that

in the 20th century due to influence of German pronunciation and was later replaced by the variant *sport* with a more English pronunciation) has been promoted as “more Croatian” mainly in the 1990’s in official usage but this prescripteme has now been mostly abandoned – even the official name of the ‘Ministry of tourism and sport’ is now *Ministarstvo turizma i sporta* (<https://mint.gov.hr/> – in the past this ministry used the variant *šport*). The prescripteme *pogrješka* (though it appears historically e.g. in Vuk’s dictionary) is nowadays used in Croatia only as a rare stylistic marker in language usage of politically right-wing people. The variant *glasati* is still commonly used in everyday language and in the standard dialect, but the prescripteme *glasovati* can also be found in official usage because some speakers perceive it as more “correct” or standard (due to prescriptivist propaganda).

³⁹ Of course, these are not the only special features of Montenegrin (some of them appear also outside of Montenegro, but are typical of Montenegrin), even if many of them are not always explicitly recognized (cf. e.g. Hickey, 2023: 140–141 for New Zealand English and its implicit norms). Such features are use of *nijesam* ‘I am not’ instead of *nisam*, frequent usage of aorist and imperfect (waning in official and public language due to influence of Serbian), *biše* ‘would’ instead of *bi* in the 3rd person plural of the conditional, clitic dative plural *ni* ‘to us’, *vi* ‘to you’, *činjeti* ‘to do’ instead of *činiti*, lexical traits such as *no* ‘but’ instead of *nego*, etc.

⁴⁰ The variants *kozji* and *koziji* (with the suffix *-(i)ji*) are a representative of a common Štokavian isoglosse (deriving from older **-ъјъъ*).

⁴¹ Montenegrin linguists are proud to point out that Montenegrin orthography is “the most democratic in the region” (cf. e.g. Šušanj, 2023: 508).

⁴² Changes in Croatian orthographies are also usually (at least at first) introduced as variant (e.g. <ne ću> ‘I won’t together with <neću>).

is actually used in living Montenegrin. The „neo-Montenegrin” standardization (*đed, šever, koži*) is often presented by its opponents as a 19th century style nationalist fabrication, language features which are present only in rural areas, something that maybe occurs in language but is not consistent, not everybody uses it, etc. In reality, forms like *đed, šever, koži* and the phonemes *š* and *ž* are used in spontaneous speech (and can be heard also in public and official circumstances as features of colloquial language as well) of practically all Montenegrins, regardless of the local dialect (including both rural and urban areas), age, social status, education, political and national identity⁴³. Both post-Yugoslav and international scholars who deal with Montenegrin in their research should be aware of this (which is not always the case nowadays) and should accordingly potentially reevaluate their positions and base their conclusions on realistic appraisal of basic linguistic facts. To put it more simply: “everybody says *đed* and *šekira* in Montenegro”. It is not an artificial made-up prescripteme that crazy nationalists are trying to force the whole population to use – this is how real Montenegrins, unless they are trying to be very careful when they are speaking (as taught in schools exclusively before the introduction of “neo-Montenegrin” standardization), talk.⁴⁴ This colloquial feature of Montenegrin was ridiculed and censored for a long time (and still is to a point by the opponents of “neo-Montenegrin” standardization), but nonetheless it has persevered – even in the cities, including the capital of Podgorica, and in the language of the youngest generations as well (cf. Šušanj, 2023: 483).⁴⁵

⁴³ The only words where there is no third jotation in pronunciation are literary words (borrowed into everyday speech from the standard dialect) such as *djelo* ‘work’ or *djeljiv* ‘divisible’ – however, these are written only as <djelo> and <djeljiv> according to the Montenegrin orthography.

⁴⁴ A traditional feature of Montenegrin was also e.g. the adjectival-pronominal ending genitive plural *-ijeh* (instead of *-ih*). However, while it still exists, this ending is nowadays less used and even archaic (just like the typically Montenegrin word *đetić* ‘young man’) due to the influence of the standard dialect (which previously usually did not take into account local Montenegrin features, which could then result in their loss). If somebody was trying to force the whole population to use *-ijeh* instead of *-ih* nowadays that would indeed be artificial and prescriptivist – but that is not actually the case in Montenegrin.

⁴⁵ These features can also be heard in public speaking even by those who are otherwise very much against the “neo-Montenegrin” standardization politically (Šušanj, 2023: 480) simply because it is a ubiquitous feature of colloquial language and

In reality, “neo-Montenegrin” standardization is very much in tune with modern (socio)linguistics and its appreciation of realistic spoken language and anti-prescriptivism. Thus, while Croatian prescriptivists, for instance, generally dislike and despise Croatian as it is actually spoken, the proponents of Montenegrin positively appraise the real Montenegrin vernacular and generally do not try to enforce artificial rules in the standard variety (or do so less than is the case elsewhere), which paints quite a different picture than what is sometimes claimed. In fact, one can also say that modern “neo-Montenegrin” standardization takes Vuk and his famous slogan *piši kako govoriš* (‘write as you speak’), or *piši kako zboriš* (in its Montenegrin version), at its words (cf. also Greenberg, 2021: 34).

Conclusion

As already mentioned, the question of language names in former Yugoslavia is mostly symbolic. In practice, the language situation does not really change whether one claims that Bosnian, Croatian, Montenegrin and Serbian are varieties of one polycentric language or distinct standard languages, which are very similar. In the end, there can be no forced language unity if the speakers are (at the time) not up for it and one cannot nor should not prohibit speakers of a language using the name they want for their language – in any case, different names for very similar language varieties are nothing new or strange in the world⁴⁶. What is more, even if it was indeed just one uniform language, with no differences at all, it can still have more than one (national) name. Likewise, if a country wants to implement a separate language standardization (if we need standardization at all), have its own grammars and dictionaries, and does not want to coordinate the standardization with neighboring countries, there is nothing an outsider can really do or should do about it.⁴⁷ One can think whatever about various

such features are not easily eliminated from usage consistently and without trace.

⁴⁶ Cf. e.g. the case of Catalan and Valencian in Spain – neither has a national state but still there are different sociolinguistic perspectives of them. Some consider Valencian as just a variety of a wider Catalan, while others insist on it being a separate language. The differences between the two or on par with the differences between different Štokavian standard varieties.

⁴⁷ The issue of local identity on one side and wider communication on the other is

nationalist policies, but the speakers have to right to standardize the way they actually speaking, whether the official ideology claims something is just a variety of a polycentric standard or a separate standard variety. For example, Americans have to right to have their own special traits in American English – just like that, Montenegrins have to right to write as they speak (if they want to), regardless of what somebody in Belgrade thinks about that. Professional linguists can have their own opinion on the problem and sociolinguistics should debunk nationalist and other language myths⁴⁸, but the question is in the end very much so political⁴⁹ – as names of languages quite often are, language being, after all, as the saying goes, a dialect with an army and a navy.⁵⁰

And finally, when speaking about nationalism in language, it is crucial to keep in mind that not all nationalisms and nationalist policies are the same. Nationalism of the oppressor is not the same as nationalism of the oppressed. Aggressive expansionist nationalism is not the same as progressive nationalism fighting for its freedom of, for instance, speaking one's own language. Nationalist agendas in language that promote artificial prescriptemes that nobody actually uses in normal language are not the same as nationalist agendas espousing actually existing language elements. Former Yugoslavia, especially Montenegro, remains a fascinating ground where one can observe a complex interaction of nationalism, nation-building (still in process in Montenegro), other ideologies and language, and where there is more to the actual situation than meets the eye.

not something typical for Montenegro, of course – cf. e.g. the same kind of dichotomy with Singapore English (Schneider, 2023: 115). A broadly similar kind of sociolinguistic strife can be found e.g. in the case of Austrian German with its own characteristics as opposed to the traditional German standard (Dollinger, 2023).

⁴⁸ However, a fruitful (and necessary) deconstruction of nationalist myths cannot ensue without first accepting everyone's really-existing national identities as equal (cf. Kapović, 2023b).

⁴⁹ Čirgić (2023: 6) openly admits that Standard Montenegrin is a political issue in Montenegro – however, he quite rightly adds (with arguments) that the same was true for Standard Serbo-Croatian in Yugoslavia.

⁵⁰ Cf. Maxwell (2018) for a complex history of this oft-cited remark.

References

- Anderson, B. (2006). *Imagined Communities. Reflections on the Origin and Spread of Nationalism*. London–New York: Verso.
- ARj (1881–1976) = *Rječnik hrvatskoga ili srpskoga jezika*, vol. 1–97 [parts I–XXIII], Zagreb: JAZU.
- Brozović, D. & Ivić, P. (1988). *Jezik, srpskohrvatski/hrvatskosrpski, hrvatski ili srpski*. Zagreb: Jugoslavenski leksikografski zavod „Miroslav Krleža“.
- Čirgić, A. (2007). *Govor podgoričkih muslimana (sinhrona i dijahrona perspektiva)*. Cetinje: Institut za crnogorski jezik i jezikoslovlje „Vojislav P. Nikčević“.
- Čirgić, A. (2011). *Montenegrin language in the past and present*. Podgorica: ICJK – Matica crnogorska.
- Čirgić, A. (2020). *Dialectology of the Montenegrin language*. Lanham–Boulder–New York–London: Lexington books.
- Čirgić, A. (2023). „Crnogorski jezički standard u analizi Milorada Pupovca“, *Lingua Montenegrina* XVI/1/31, p. 3–22.
- Długosz, N. (2023). „Goranci (Gorani), Language of the“, in: Marc L. Greenberg & Lenore A. Grenoble (Eds), *Encyclopedia of Slavic Languages and Linguistics Online* [http://dx.doi.org/10.1163/2589-6229_ESLO_COM_036103]
- Dollinger, S. (2023). „Prescriptivism and national identity: Socio-historical constructionism, disciplinary blindspots, and Standard Austrian German“, in: Beal, Joan C., Lukač, Morana & Straaijer, Robin (Eds), *The Routledge Handbook of Linguistic Prescriptivism*. London–New York: Routledge, str. 121–139.
- Glušica, R. (2020). *Crnogorski jezik i nacionalizam*, Biblioteka XX vek, Beograd.
- Greenberg, R. (2004). *Language and identity in the Balkans: Serbo-Croatian and its disintegration*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Greenberg, R. (2021). „Standard language ideology and the south Slavic standard languages of the former Yugoslavia“, in: Vujović, N. (ed.), *Cetinjski filološki dani II (zbornik radova s naučnoga skupa održanog na Cetinju 10–12. septembra 2019)*. Cetinje: FCJK–KU, p. 21–41.

- Hickey, R. (2023). „Standards with pluricentric languages: Who sets norms and where“, in: Beal, Joan C., Lukač, Morana & Straaijer, Robin (Eds), *The Routledge Handbook of Linguistic Prescriptivism*. London–New York: Routledge, p. 140–156.
- Hodžić, J. (2023). „Pitanje odmaka od Novosadskog dogovora u Bosni i Hercegovini sedamdesetih godina prošlog vijeka“, *Lingua Montenegrina*, XVI/1/31, str. 23–38
- Kaldellis, A. (2008). *Hellenism in Byzantium. The Transformations of Greek Identity and the Reception of the Classical Tradition*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Kapović, M. (2011a). *Čiji je jezik?*. Zagreb: Algoritam.
- Kapović, M. (2011b). „Language, Ideology and Politics in Croatia“, *Slavia centralis* IV/2, p. 45–56.
- Kapović, M. (2015). *Povijest hrvatske akcentuacije. Fonetika*. Zagreb: Matica hrvatska.
- Kapović, M. (2016). „Language, Linguistics, Nationalism and Science“, *Etnološka tribina: Godišnjak Hrvatskog etnološkog društva* 46/39, p. 25–30.
- Kapović, M. (2017). „The Position of Kajkavian in the South Slavic Dialect Continuum in Light of Old Accentual Isoglosses“, *Zeitschrift für Slawistik* 62/4, p. 606–620.
- Kapović, M. (2018). „The Unattainable Standard – Zagreb Dialect Meets Standard Croatian Accentuation“, *Slověne. International Journal of Slavic Studies* 7/1, p. 337–362.
- Kapović, M. (2020). „Bosnian/Croatian/Montenegrin/Serbian: Notes on contact and conflict“, in: Muhr, Rudolf; Mas Castells, Josep Àngel & Rueter, Jack (Eds), *European Pluricentric Languages in Contact and Conflict*. Berlin: Peter Lang, p. 171–184.
- Kapović, M. (2022). „Bilješke o akcentološkim istraživanjima u Crnoj Gori“, in: Vujović, Novica (ed.), *Cetinjski filološki dani III, zbornik radova s naučnoga skupa održanog na Cetinju 2. i 3. septembra 2021.*, Cetinje: KU/Department of Slavic and Eurasian Languages & Literatures–FCJK, p. 285–302.
- Kapović, M. (2023a). *Uvod u fonologiju*, Zagreb: Sandorf.
- Kapović, M. (2023b). „Od nacionalizma do jezika i natrag“, *Res publica* [<https://respublicacasopis.net/2023/02/08/od-nacionalizma-do-jezika-i-natrag/>]

- Kordić, S. (2010). *Jezik i nacionalizam*. Zagreb: Durieux.
- Kordić, S. (2024). „Ideology Against Language: The Current Situation in South Slavic Countries“, in: Nomachi, Motoki & Kamusella, Tomasz (Eds), *Languages and Nationalism Instead of Empires*. New York: Routledge, p. 167–179.
- Maxwell, A. (2018). „When Theory is a Joke: The Weinreich Witticism in Linguistics“, *Beiträge zur Geschichte der Sprachwissenschaft* 28/2, p. 263–292.
- PGHKJ (1979) = Peti, M. et al. (1979). *Priručna gramatika hrvatskoga književnog jezika*. Zagreb: Školska knjiga.
- Pupovac, M. (2022). „Vernakulari država i diskursi nacija: rasprava povodom knjige Rajke Glušice *Crnogorski jezik i nacionalizam*“, *Tragovi* 5/2, p. 175–220.
- Schneider, Edgar W. (2023). „The role of prescriptivism in the emergence of New Englishes“, in: Beal, Joan C., Lukač, Morana & Straaijer, Robin (Eds), *The Routledge Handbook of Linguistic Prescriptivism*. London–New York: Routledge, p. 103–120.
- Starčević, A. & Kapović, M. & Sarić, D. (2023). „Prescriptivism in Croatia“, in: Beal, Joan C.; Lukač, Morana & Straaijer, Robin (Eds), *The Routledge Handbook of Linguistic Prescriptivism*. London–New York: Routledge, p. 386–404.
- Šistek, F. (2015). *Narativi o identitetu. Izabrane studije o crnogorskoj istoriji*. Podgorica: Matica crnogorska.
- Šušanj, J. (2022). „Standardni jezik kao poprište manipulacija – prilog jednoj polemici“, in: Vujović, N. (Ed.) *Cetinjski filološki dani III (zbornik radova s međunarodnoga naučnog simpozijuma održanog na Cetinju 2. i 3. septembra 2021)*. Cetinje: KU–FCJK, p. 477–510.
- Težak, S. & Babić, S. (1971⁴). *Pregled gramatike hrvatskosrpskog jezika za osnovne i druge škole*. Zagreb: Školska knjiga.
- Todorova, M. (2009²). *Imagining the Balkans*, Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Trudgill, P. (2000⁴). *Sociolinguistics: An Introduction to Language and Society*. London–New York: Penguin Books.
- Vermeer, W. (1982). „On the principal sources for the study of Čakavian dialects with neocircumflex in adjectives and *e*-presents“, *Studies in Slavic and General Linguistics* 2, p. 279–340.

- Vujić, N. (2023). „Crnogorski jezik između nauke i manipulacije“, *Kolo* XXXIII/1, p. 273–280.
- Vuk = Вук Стеф. Караџић (1935⁴). *Српски рјечник истумачен њемачкијем и латинскијем ријечима*. Београд: Штампарија Краљевине Југославије.
- Wiese, H. (2023). *Grammatical systems without language borders: Lessons from free-range language*. Berlin: Language Science Press.